

CHEMICAL AND BACTERIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF WASTEWATER FROM RESOURCES IMPROVEMENT AND MANUFACTURING COMPANY (RIMCO), NNEWI, ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

This research work was on the chemical and bacteriological analysis of effluents from Resources Improvement and Manufacturing Company, Nnewi using the World Health Organisation (WHO) standard (1993) for drinking water and the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME) standard (1999) for irrigated crops and aquatic life criteria respectively. The effluent samples from the company were collected and series of chemical and bacteriological tests were conducted. Samples were collected from three different sources. The results of the series of tests and analyses showed that a number of parameters tested such as iron, lead, manganese, turbidity, colour, etc. were higher than the WHO standards for drinking water. Parameters like turbidity, Total Suspended Solid (TSS), and chloride were higher and some like sulphates were lower than the recommended Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME) standard for irrigation. Again, parameters like dissolved oxygen, nitrate and pH were lower and some like turbidity and iron were higher than the recommended CCME standards for aquatic life. The total Coliform and *E. coli* count per 100ml were higher than limit set for irrigated crops using the CCME criterion. It is, therefore, recommended that the effluents from Resources Improvement and Manufacturing Company should be treated to an intended standard before been discharged to the environment. It is also recommended that further work on this should be focused in the area of aquatic life and irrigation water which were not well covered in this work.

KEYWORDS:- Coliform, Effluent, Environment, Parameter Sample, Standard.

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INTRODUCTION

The need for a clean environment is very paramount for both humans, animals, plants, soils, etc, hence the need for the wastewater from our environment to be properly treated before they are released into the environment. The impact of industrial wastewater discharges on the environment and human population can be tragic at times. Some 50 years ago, the Minamata disease which spread among residents in the Yatsushiro Sea and the Agano River basin areas in Japan was attributed to methyl mercury in industrial wastewater (Matsuo, 1999).

Agro-industrial wastewaters, as a sub-class of industrial wastewaters, can have considerable impact on the environment because they can be very strong in terms of pollutant strength and often the scale of the industry generating the wastewater in a country is large. Citing ASEAN countries in Asia as examples, agro-industrial wastewaters had and in some instances still contribute very significantly to pollution loads. For example in 1981 the

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Malaysian palm oil and rubber industries contributed 63% (1460 td/1) and 7% (208td/1) of the BOD (Biochemical Oxygen Demand) load generated per day respectively. This is compared with 715 td/1 of BOD from domestic sewage. In the Philippines, pulp and paper mills generated 90 td/1 of BOD load. Agro-industrial sites are therefore often the largest easily identifiable point sources of pollutant loads (Wun, 2012).

For Resources Improvement and Manufacturing Company (RIMCO), an agro –allied manufacturing company which deals with edible products, there is great need for much emphasis to be made so as to eliminate or minimize to the bearest minimum the toxic effluents being discharged into the immediate environment. This can be achieved by treating these effluents properly before discharge. The wastewater from RIMCO exits at two main places. The places include the refinery unit where the crude oil is refined and the solvent extraction unit where oil is totally extracted from the palm kernel cake using hexane.

Traditionally, industrial processes were designed in the absence of consideration to wastes produced or the potential environmental impact that they may cause (Unnikrishnan, 2005). This was so because there were little or no wastewater treatment industries where these wastewaters could be treated and most importantly, there were few or no water boards where these wastewaters can be tested to determine and analyse their actual constituents and effect before treatment.

In other words, the chemical and biological characteristics of industrial wastewater are of major importance in determining the effects on the immediate environment and the importance of treating them before discharge. Industrial wastewater contains suspended colloidal and dissolved (mineral and organic) solids, excessive acid or excessive alkaline, toxic materials, pathogenic bacteria and so many other substances. The direct discharge of this waste water is harmful to the human body, crops, animals and plants beyond a specific limit. This study was conducted to know the chemical and biological properties of wastewater obtained from Resources improvement and Manufacturing Company and to analyse the effects on the immediate environment.

Resources Improvement and manufacturing Company was the first vegetable oil company in Nnewi. The company started with the production of life vegetable oil to the production of ideal vegetable oil and palm olien oil. The company has no treatment unit. Owing to this, waste water discharge from the plant flows down directly to farmlands and to a river known as Mmiri-ele River. However, over the years, these direct discharges from the company have affected the farmlands along that area and have also affected the quality of the Mmiri-ele River.

The introduction of a waste water treatment plant will go a long way in the alleviation of hazards caused to human health and to plants and animals, hence the need to test and analyse the waste water. The World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME) standards will be used as a guide.

The discharge of untreated wastewater directly into the environment from Resources Improvement and Manufacturing Company is not healthy to the environment. These wastewaters need to be properly treated before they are released into environment to prevent environmental pollution. The provision of a wastewater treatment plant will go a long way in solving these problems and will make our environment friendlier.

The chemical and biological properties of these wastewaters will be carried out to determine their actual constituents and the effect on the immediate environment.

The treatment of wastewater is not only important for our own health but also to keep our environment clean and healthy. Without the proper wastewater treatment many ecosystems would be severely damaged once the treated water gets recharged back into the environment (Ned, 2010).

There are many types of industrial wastewater based on different industries and the contaminants. Each sector produces its own combination of pollutants. The table below illustrates it more.

Table 1: Water pollutants by the Industrial Sector

Sector	Pollutant
Iron and steel	BOD, COD, oil, metals, acids, phenols and cyanide.
Textiles and leather	BOD, solids, sulfates and chromium.
Pulp and paper	BOD, COD, solids, chlorinated organic compounds.
Petrochemicals and refineries	BOD, COD, mineral oils, phenols and chromium.
Chemicals	COD, organic chemicals, heavy metal, SS and cyanide.
Non-ferrous metals	Fluorine, SS
Microelectronics	COD and organic chemicals.
Mining	Metal, acids and salts.

Source: Hanchang, 2002, SHI, Beijing, China. <http://www.eolss.net>

MATERIALS AND METHOD

STUDY LOCATION

Resources Improvement and Manufacturing Company is located at RIMCO Drive Chicason Avenue Akwuru-uru Industrial Estate, Umudim Nnewi. A sub-urban area of Nnewi North Local Government Area in Anambra State. This area lies approximately on the latitude of 5°59'47.39'' North of the equator and longitude 6°55'14.45'' East of the Greenwich Meridian. The terrain of this area is hilly, sloping downwards towards a river called Idemili River where most of the effluents are emptied. From that point, it travels a long distance and terminates at River Niger.

(a) Map of Nigeria showing Anambra State.

(b) Map of Anambra State showing Nnewi North Local Government Area (L.G.A).

(c) Map of Nnewi L.G.A showing RIMCO, the study Area.

(d) The discharge point into Mmiri-ele River

The analysis is to determine the chemical and bacteriological characteristics of the wastewater effluents. This was carried out in the laboratory of Enugu State Water Corporation (ENSWC), Enugu. The results obtained from the analysis of the collected wastewater sample using standard procedures are presented in the tables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

The wastewater effluents samples obtained from Resources Improvement and Manufacturing Company, after being analysed, gave the results presented in Table 2. The result comprises of the chemical and the bacteriological constituents only.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

From the comparisons presented in the Tables 3, 4 and 5, it is observed that some of the results are within the compared standards; some are above it, while some are below the standards. The effects of some of the parameters above and below the standards on the environment (specifically on humans, crops and aquatic life) will be presented in tabular forms. In Tables 6, 7 and 8, a, b and c stands for refinery waste effluent, solvent waste effluent and soil water respectively.

Table 2: Summary of sample results

S/N	PARAMETERS	UNITS	REFINERY EFFLUENT	SOLVENT EFFLUENT	SOIL WATER
	Chemical Parameters				
1	pH		6.00	4.80	7.80
2	Chlorides	Mg/l	356.27	17.02	42.54
3	Chloride as NaCl	Mg/l	587.85	28.08	70.19
4	Total hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	8.00	30.00	90.00
5	Calcium hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	0.00	25.00	83.00
6	Magnesium hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	8.00	5.00	7.00
7	Total alkalinity	Mg/lCaCO ₃	10.00	18.00	140.00
8	Iron	Mg/l	0.00	1.25	0.90
9	Sulphates	Mg/l	24.87	83.32	21.95
10	Nitrate	Mg/l	0.24	7.12	8.80
11	Silica	Mg/l	18.00	18.20	ND
12	Calcium ion	Mg/l	4.00	10.00	33.2
13	Magnesium ion	Mg/l	2.40	1.50	2.10
14	Manganese	Mg/l	1.96	0.82	ND
15	Silver	Mg/l	ND	0.01	ND
16	Copper	Mg/l	0.06	0.44	0.41
17	Zinc	Mg/l	0.19	1.37	1.24
18	DO	Mg/l	0.04	0.20	0.64
19	BOD	Mg/l	127.00	112.00	101.00
20	COD	Mg/l	185.00	235.00	110.00
21	Phenol	Mg/l	2.94	ND	ND
22	Cyanide	Mg/l	ND	ND	ND
23	Lead	Mg/l	0.14	ND	ND
24	Sodium	Mg/l	0.25	0.21	2.02
25	Phosphate	Mg/l	ND	0.79	ND
26	Nickel	Mg/l	3.05	ND	ND
27	Arsenic	Mg/l	ND	ND	ND
28	Oil and grease	Mg/l	16.79	3.26	ND
	Biological Parameters				
1	Plate count	Perml	241.00	320.00	106.00
2	Total coliform	Per100ml	7.00	94.00	>240
3	<i>E.coli</i>	Per100ml	-ve	-ve	+ve

*ND means not determined. NA means not available.

COMPARISON OF THE RESULTS OBTAINED WITH INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

Table 3: Comparison of the results with WHO Standard (1993) for drinking water

S/N	PARAMETERS	UNITS	REFINERY EFFLUENT	SOLVENT EFFLUENT	SOIL WATER	WHO STANDARD
	<u>Chemical Parameters</u>					
1	pH		6.00	4.80	7.80	6.5-8.5
2	Chlorides	Mg/l	356.27	17.02	42.54	250
3	Chloride as NaCl	Mg/l	587.85	28.08	70.19	413
4	Total hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	8.00	30.00	90.00	100-200
5	Calcium hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	0.00	25.00	83.00	200
6	Magnesium hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	8.00	5.00	7.00	12
7	Total alkalinity	Mg/lCaCO ₃	10.00	18.00	140.00	100
8	Iron	Mg/l	0.00	1.25	0.90	0.3
9	Sulphates	Mg/l	24.87	83.32	21.95	500
10	Nitrate	Mg/l	0.24	7.12	8.80	10
11	Silica	Mg/l	18.00	18.20	ND	NA
12	Calcium ion	Mg/l	4.00	10.00	33.2	50
13	Magnesium ion	Mg/l	2.40	1.50	2.10	50
14	Manganese	Mg/l	1.96	0.82	ND	0.5
15	Silver	Mg/l	ND	0.01	ND	0.10
16	Copper	Mg/l	0.06	0.44	0.41	2.0
17	Zinc	Mg/l	0.19	1.37	1.24	3
18	DO	Mg/l	0.04	0.20	0.64	NG
19	BOD	Mg/l	127.00	112.00	101.00	NG
20	COD	Mg/l	185.00	235.00	110.00	NG
21	Phenol	Mg/l	2.94	ND	ND	0.3
22	Cyanide	Mg/l	ND	ND	ND	0.07
23	Lead	Mg/l	0.14	ND	ND	0.01
24	Sodium	Mg/l	0.25	0.21	2.02	20
25	Phosphate	Mg/l	ND	0.79	ND	NA
26	Nickel	Mg/l	3.05	ND	ND	0.02
27	Arsenic	Mg/l	ND	ND	ND	0.01
28	Oil and grease	Mg/l	16.79	3.26	ND	0.05
	<u>Biological Parameters</u>					
1	Plate count	Perml	241.00	320.00	106.00	100
2	Total coliform	Per100ml	7.00	94.00	>240	3.0
3	<i>E.coli</i>	Per100ml	-ve	-ve	+ve	0.0

*ND means not determined. NA means not available.

Table 4: Comparison of the results with CCME standard (1999) for irrigation (crops)

S/N	PARAMETERS	UNITS	REFINERY EFFLUENT	SOLVENT EFFLUENT	SOIL WATER	CCME STANDARD
	<u>Chemical Parameters</u>					
1	pH		6.00	4.80	7.80	5.5-8.5
2	Chlorides	Mg/l	356.27	17.02	42.54	100
3	Chloride as NaCl	Mg/l	587.85	28.08	70.19	165
4	Total hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	8.00	30.00	90.00	500
5	Calcium hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	0.00	25.00	83.00	NA
6	Magnesium hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	8.00	5.00	7.00	NA
7	Total alkalinity	Mg/lCaCO ₃	10.00	18.00	140.00	
8	Iron	Mg/l	0.00	1.25	0.90	5.0
9	Sulphates	Mg/l	24.87	83.32	21.95	<2000
10	Nitrate	Mg/l	0.24	7.12	8.80	10
11	Silica	Mg/l	18.00	18.20	ND	NA
12	Calcium ion	Mg/l	4.00	10.00	33.2	<800
13	Magnesium ion	Mg/l	2.40	1.50	2.10	<120
14	Manganese	Mg/l	1.96	0.82	ND	0.2 – 2.0
15	Silver	Mg/l	ND	0.01	ND	NA
16	Copper	Mg/l	0.06	0.44	0.41	0.2
17	Zinc	Mg/l	0.19	1.37	1.24	2.0
18	DO	Mg/l	0.04	0.20	0.64	NA
19	BOD	Mg/l	127.00	112.00	101.00	<100
20	COD	Mg/l	185.00	235.00	110.00	<150
21	Phenol	Mg/l	2.94	ND	ND	NA
22	Cyanide	Mg/l	ND	ND	ND	NA
23	Lead	Mg/l	0.14	ND	ND	0.2
24	Sodium	Mg/l	0.25	0.21	2.02	8 -18
25	Phosphate	Mg/l	ND	0.79	ND	NA
26	Nickel	Mg/l	3.05	ND	ND	0.2
27	Arsenic	Mg/l	ND	ND	ND	0.1
28	Oil and grease	Mg/l	16.79	3.26	ND	NA
	<u>Biological Parameters</u>					
1	Plate count	Perml	241.00	320.00	106.00	NA
2	Total coliform	Per100ml	7.00	94.00	>240	1.0
3	<i>E.coli</i>	Per100ml	-ve	-ve	+ve	0.1

*ND means not determined. NA means not available.

Table 5: Comparison of the results with CCME standard (1999) for aquatic life

S/N	PARAMETERS	UNITS	REFINERY EFFLUENT	SOLVENT EFFLUENT	SOIL WATER	CCME STANDARD
	<u>Chemical Parameters</u>					
1	pH		6.00	4.80	7.80	6.5 – 9.0
2	Chlorides	Mg/l	356.27	17.02	42.54	120
3	Chloride as NaCl	Mg/l	587.85	28.08	70.19	198
4	Total hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	8.00	30.00	90.00	NA
5	Calcium hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	0.00	25.00	83.00	NA
6	Magnesium hardness	Mg/lCaCO ₃	8.00	5.00	7.00	NA
7	Total alkalinity	Mg/lCaCO ₃	10.00	18.00	140.00	NA
8	Iron	Mg/l	0.00	1.25	0.90	0.3
9	Sulphates	Mg/l	24.87	83.32	21.95	NA
10	Nitrate	Mg/l	0.24	7.12	8.80	13
11	Silica	Mg/l	18.00	18.20	ND	NA
12	Calcium ion	Mg/l	4.00	10.00	33.2	NA
13	Magnesium ion	Mg/l	2.40	1.50	2.10	NA
14	Manganese	Mg/l	1.96	0.82	ND	NA
15	Silver	Mg/l	ND	0.01	ND	0.0001
16	Copper	Mg/l	0.06	0.44	0.41	NA
17	Zinc	Mg/l	0.19	1.37	1.24	0.03
18	DO	Mg/l	0.04	0.20	0.64	6.8
19	BOD	Mg/l	127.00	112.00	101.00	4.0
20	COD	Mg/l	185.00	235.00	110.00	NA
21	Phenol	Mg/l	2.94	ND	ND	0.005
22	Cyanide	Mg/l	ND	ND	ND	0.005
23	Lead	Mg/l	0.14	ND	ND	1.7
24	Sodium	Mg/l	0.25	0.21	2.02	NA
25	Phosphate	Mg/l	ND	0.79	ND	NA
26	Nickel	Mg/l	3.05	ND	ND	0.025 - 0.15
27	Arsenic	Mg/l	ND	ND	ND	0.5
28	Oil and grease	Mg/l	16.79	3.26	ND	NA
	<u>Biological Parameters</u>					
1	Plate count	Per ml	241.00	320.00	106.00	NA
2	Total coliform	Per 100ml	7.00	94.00	>240	NA
3	<i>E.coli</i>	Per 100ml	-ve	-ve	+ve	NA

*ND means not determined. NA means not available.

Table 6: Effects of some constituents on humans

S/N	Parameters	Level in Comparison with WHO Standard for Drinking Water	Effects on Humans
1	Turbidity (a) (b)	Greatly higher Greatly higher	Aesthetically displeasing in the sense that nobody likes the look of dirty water. High turbidity indicates possible bacterial contamination (NDDH, 2005).
2	Nitrate (a) (b)	Greatly lower Slightly lower	When taken in excess of the standard by infants below six months can lead to illness (methemoglobinemia) and if untreated can cause death (USEPA, 2012).
3	Colour (a) (b)	Greatly higher Greatly higher	Aesthetically displeasing. Coloured water may be due to the presence of coloured organic substances such as iron, copper, etc. (GNWT, 2011).
4	Copper (a) (b)	Greatly lower Greatly lower	Copper deficiencies result in a variety of clinical disorders including nutritional anaemia in infants. Copper helps in human metabolism (GNWT, 2011).
5	Chloride (a) (b)	Greatly higher Greatly lower	Excess chloride above standard may result in an objectionable salty taste to water. It may cause corrosion in distribution system (NDDH, 2005).
6	Iron (a) (b)	Not Available Greatly higher	When in excess, it makes water to taste bad can cause staining of laundry and plumbing fixtures. Deficiency can result in impaired mental development in children and impaired work, performances in adults (GNWT, 2011).
7	Lead (a) (b)	Greatly higher Not Available	Negatively affects the central nervous system. Pregnant women, infants and children are most vulnerable (GNWT, 2011).
8	Manganese (a) (b)	Greatly higher Slightly higher	It produces undesirable tastes in water and drinks, stains laundry and plumbing fixtures (GNWT, 2011).
9	pH (a) (b)	Slightly lower Greatly lower	Corrosiveness of water generally increases with decreasing pH, and it is considered acidic (GWIC, 2012).
10	Sodium (a) (b)	Greatly lower Greatly lower	Sodium helps maintain water balance in human body but when in excess in drinking water, it makes the water to taste bad (NDDH, 2005).
11	Phenols (a) (b)	Greatly higher Not available	It imparts a medicinal taste and odour to water when latter is chlorinated (EPA, 2012).

Table 7: Effects of some constituents on crops

S/N	Parameters	Level in Comparison with CCME Standard for Irrigation Water	Effects on Crops
1	pH (a) (b) (c)	Normal Slightly lower normal	Low pH may cause accelerated irrigation system corrosion where they occur (Bauder <i>et al</i> , 2012).
2	Chloride (a) (b) (c)	Greatly higher Greatly lower Greatly lower	At very low amounts, chloride is very essential to plants but at high content, it can cause toxicity to sensitive crops. It causes more problems when applied with sprinkler irrigation just like sodium (Bauder <i>et al</i> , 2012).
3	Sulphate (a) (b) (c)	Greatly lower Greatly lower Greatly lower	Sulphate in irrigation water has fertility benefits so absence of it indicates absence of the benefits (Bauder <i>et al</i> , 2012).
4	TSS (a) (b) (c)	Greatly higher Greatly higher Not available	The higher the total suspended solids in water, the murkier it seems and the higher the turbidity (Lenntech, 2011).
5	Turbidity (a) (b) (c)	Greatly higher Greatly higher Not available	Higher turbidity indicates higher suspended solids which scatter the light thus, decreasing the photosynthetic activity of plants which contributes to lowering the oxygen concentration and even more (Lenntech, 2011).

Table 8: Effects of some constituents on aquatic life

S/N	Parameters	Level in Comparison with CCME Standard for Aquatic Life	Effects on Aquatic Life
1	Dissolved oxygen (a) (b)	Greatly lower Greatly lower	Aquatic animals need dissolved oxygen to live because it is required for respiration. Dissolved oxygen reduces with increase in temperature because most living organisms increase their activity in warm water (Anon, 2012b).
2	Nitrate (a) (b)	Greatly lower Slightly lower	It is essential for plant growth, but the presence of excessive amounts in water supplies presents a major pollution problem (Anon, 2012b).
3	pH (a) (b)	Normal Slightly lower	pH below the standards is harmful to shrimp, snails and clams. Metals normally trapped in sediments may be released into acidified water (Anon, 2012b).
4	Turbidity (a) (b)	Greatly higher Greatly higher	As a consequence of the particles settling to the bottom, shallow lakes fill in faster, fish eggs and insect larvae are covered and suffocated, gill structures get clogged or damaged. Also suspended particles absorb heat from the sunlight, making turbid water become warmer and so reducing the concentration of oxygen in the water (Lenntech, 2011).
5	Iron (a) (b)	Not available Greatly higher	High values of iron in streams may indicate contamination from landfills (Anon, 2012b).
6	BOD (a) (b)	Greatly higher Greatly higher	When in excess, it can cause anaerobic conditions, which leads to noxious odours. It reduces dissolved oxygen concentrations in water to levels that cause fish to suffocate. It also leads to overall degradation of water quality (Lenntech, 2011).

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